

Concrete Syntax

LEMON

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1. Language in BNF

The language used here to define the concrete syntax is based on BNF (see https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Erweiterte_Backus-Naur-Form). For the sake of completeness, the most important rules are summarized here:

Verwendung	Zeichen
Alternative	
Option	[...]
Optional repetition, as often as required	{...}
Optional repetition, but min. once	{...}+
Repetition m times	{...} ^m
Repetition m to n times	{...} ^{m..n}
Grouping for better readability	(...)

For non-terminal symbols in italic bold letters, DO NOT insert spaces between the symbols.

2. Basic objectives and rules

The language is to be as intuitive as possible, easily learnable. It must be able to be "fitted" as a framework into the graphic module language of Posity and other MDD tools. LEMON is a Language for spEcifying **MO**del patter**NS**. LEMON has two uses:

- **Documentation of knowledge:** LEMON describes model patterns.
- **Creating models:** LEMON allows the creation of new models based on previously described model patterns.

We answer the following questions to specify the LEMON objectives:

- **Who will model in the DSL?** PDS developers.
- **Who is going to review the models?** Lexical, syntactic, and syntax analyzers will automatically check LEMON models.
- **When are the models going to be reviewed?** During the modeling specification. If it is feasible, it should be near-to-real-time.
- **Who is using the models for which purpose?** PDS developers for specifying model patterns and later reusing them, improving model creation quality and speed based on well-specified model patterns.

The concrete syntax reuses PosityScript language elements, strongly reminiscent of Minimal Basic (ECMA-55). Moreover, we reuse elements from other languages such as the EMOF (Essential Meta Object Facility) and ones found in the literature. Basic:

- The language is case sensitive
- The commands (statements) are not terminated by ";" but must be in separate lines.

Moreover, LEMON is a platform-independent language. However, LEMON allows specifying several Metamodels, including the Posity metamodel. Then, PDS developers can represent model patterns by using such LEMON compliant Metamodels.

3. Keywords

The keywords are colored green (inherit from PosityScript) and colored blue (new keywords based on Ecore and other sources) to make the following table a bit clearer. A keyword is an expression that has its own meaning and cannot be used as an identifier or subroutine name. Keywords must be free-standing (spaces before and after the keyword).

and	date	endsub
blob	dateandtime	endtry
bool	duration	false
breakif	else	foreach
case	endcase	gosub
catch	endforeach	if
dataset	endif	in
default	endloop	like

loop	type	applypattern
money	default	having as input
none	endattribute	having as output
not	reference	endapplypattern
number	ordered	ask
of	unique	inputlist
or	keys	endinputlist
sub	lowerbound	outputlist
text	upperbound	endoutputlist
then	endreference	null
time	endclass	endoutputlist
to	datatype	select
true	enddatatype	where
try	endmetamodel	distinct
when	new	join
xor	remove	query
//	from	endquery
/*...*/	metadata	checking
metamodel	name	endchecking
enum	description	check
literal	keywords	abstract
value	endmetadata	list
endliteral	pattern	domain
endenum	endpattern	import
class	apply	as
supertypes	endapply	extra
operation	input	endextra
exceptions	defaultvalue	expected
type	endinput	endexpected
endoperation	output	
attribute	endoutput	

4th Variable declaration and priority

If variables are declared without initialization, they are initialized with the data type-dependent default value. Variables can be defined in the code block, in the apply pattern method, in the module itself, or globally in the application. With identical names, code block variables are addressed before module variables before global variables.

5. Operator priority

The operators have the following priority:

1. ()
2. not
3. *, /
4. +, -
5. <, <=, >, >=, ==, <>, like
6. and
7. or
8. xor

If several operators of the same priority occur, the left operator has priority over the right one. E.G.

$3 + 4 - 3 \rightarrow$ plus before minus

$3 - 4 + 3 \rightarrow$ minus vor Plus

6. Grammar

Symbole	Regel
metamodel_def	metamodel metamodel_name new_line {metamodel_def_stmt} endmetamodel
metamodel_def_stmt	metamodel_enum_def metamodel_class_def metamodel_datatype_def
metamodel_enum_def	enum enum_name new_line {metamodel_enum_literal_def}+ endenum
metamodel_enum_literal_def	literal literal_name new_line value number_term new_line endliteral
metamodel_class_def	class ([abstract] [domain]) class_name [supertypes {class_name} ¹ ... [*]] new_line {metamodel_class_def_stmt} endclass
metamodel_class_def_stmt	metamodel_class_operation_def metamodel_class_attribute_def metamodel_class_reference_def
metamodel_class_operation_def	operation operation_name new_line [exceptions {class_name} ¹ ... [*] new_line] type data_type datatype_name new_line endoperation
metamodel_class_attribute_def ^P	attribute attribute_name new_line type data_type datatype_name new_line [default term new_line] primarykey bool_term new_line tooltype text_term new_line endattribute

Symbole	Regel
metamodel_class_reference_def ^q	<pre> reference reference_name new_line type class_name new_line ordered bool_term new_line unique bool_term new_line keys {class_name.attribute_name}^{1...*} new_line lowerbound number_term new_line upperbound number_term "*" new_line endreference </pre>
metamodel_datatype_def	<pre> datatype datatype_name new_line [default term] new_line enddatatype </pre>
pattern_def	<pre> [{new_line}] {import_stmt} pattern pattern_name new_line metadata_stmt new_line {pattern_def_stmt} endpattern {subroutine} </pre>
pattern_def_stmt	(pattern_input_stmt pattern_output_stmt apply_stmt apply_pattern_stmt) new_line
metadata_stmt	<pre> metadata new_line name text_term new_line description text_term new_line keywords text_term {"," text_term}^{0...*} new_line endmetadata </pre>
import_stmt	import_metamodel_stmt import_pattern_stmt
import_metamodel_stmt	import metamodel metamodel_name from text_term new_line
import_pattern_stmt	import pattern pattern_name from text_term new_line
pattern_input_stmt	pattern_single_input_stmt pattern_list_input_stmt
pattern_output_stmt	pattern_single_output_stmt pattern_list_output_stmt

Symbole	Regel
pattern_single_input_stmt	input input_name new_line type data_type new_line description text_term new_line [query new_line query_select_command new_line new_line endquery new_line] {input_data_def_stmt} ^{0...*} [defaultvalue term new_line] endinput
input_data_def_stmt	extra_stmt expected_stmt checking_stmt
pattern_single_output_stmt	output output_name new_line type data_type new_line description text_term new_line {checking_stmt} ^{0...*} [defaultvalue term new_line] endoutput
pattern_list_input_stmt	inputlist input_name new_line type data_type new_line description text_term new_line [query new_line query_select_command new_line new_line endquery new_line] {input_data_def_stmt} ^{0...*} [defaultvalue list_term new_line] endinputlist
pattern_list_output_stmt	outputlist output_name new_line type data_type new_line description text_term new_line {checking_stmt} ^{0...*} [defaultvalue list_term new_line] endoutputlist
apply_stmt	apply new_line {codeblock} {checking_stmt} ^{0...*} endapply

Symbole	Regel
checking_stmt ^a	checking checking_name new_line {checking_stmt_def} endchecking
checking_stmt_def	{stmt}* {check_stmt}*
check_stmt	check condition else text_term new_line
codeblock ^b	[{new_line}] {stmt} ⁺
codeblock_var_def ^c	data_type codeblock_var [codeblock_var_init] {"," codeblock_var [codeblock_var_init]} new_line
data_type	number money text bool dateandtime date time duration dataset blob metamodel_class_ref_datatype metamodel_datatype_ref_datatype metamodel_enum_datatype
metamodel_class_ref_datatype	class metamodel_name"."class_name
metamodel_datatype_ref_datatype	datatype metamodel_name"."datatype_name
metamodel_enum_datatype	enum metamodel_name"."enum_name
codeblock_var_init	"=" term
metamodel_term	new (metamodel_class_ref_datatype metamodel_datatype_ref_datatype metamodel_enum_datatype) new_line
list_term	"[" term {"," term} ^{0...*} "]"
new_line	{[comment] <i>EOL</i> ^d } ⁺
comment	// {character}

^a Inside checking_stmt can not modify the value of any variable defined outside the checking. Inside checking they can read the data. Checking_stmt cannot have other checking_stmt inside.

^p **type** and **default** must be consistent, i.e., if **type** is **number** then **default** must be a number.

^q **type** and **keys** must be consistent, i.e., if **type** is ClassA then **keys** must be a subset of ClassA attributes such as ClassA.B, ClassA.C, etc.

^b Single start symbol of the language (from this the whole code is derived).

^c Declaration of variables which are only used within this code block.

^d End-of-Line: Wrap to next line (control character).

Symbole	Regel
stmt	(codeblock_var_def assignment_stmt if_else_stmt foreach_stmt loop_stmt case_stmt try_catch_stmt go_subroutine relate_to_stmt unrelate_from_stmt checking_stmt list_append list_remove to_datatype_stmt is_null_stmt instanceof_stmt generate_guid_stmt) new_line
to_datatype_stmt	to_number_stmt to_bool_stmt to_text_stmt to_money_stmt to_date_stmt to_datetime_stmt
to_number_stmt	tonumber "("(term identifier)")"
to_bool_stmt	tobool "("(text_term number_term bool_term identifier)")"
to_text_stmt	totext "(" (term identifier) ")"
to_money_stmt	tomoney "("(term identifier)"," text_term ^e ["," number_term"]f)"
to_date_stmt	todate "("(text_term identifier)"," text_term ^g)"
to_datetime_stmt	todatetime "("(text_term identifier)"," text_term ^h)"
is_null_stmt	isnull "("identifier")"
instanceof_stmt	identifier instanceof class_name
generate_guid_stmt	generateguid ["("(text_term identifier)")"]
relate_to_stmt	relate identifier to identifier in identifier.reference_name
unrelate_from_stmt	unrelate identifier from identifier in identifier.reference_name
apply_pattern_stmt	applypattern pattern_name [if condition] as identifier [for each identifier in identifier] new_line [having as input new_line {apply_pattern_input_stmt} ¹ ... [*]] [having as output new_line {apply_pattern_output_stmt} ¹ ... [*]] endapplypattern
apply_pattern_input_stmt	(input_name input_name.extra_name input_name.attribute_name) "=" (ask term) new_line

^e References the currency. z.B. CHF, EUR, USD, COP...

^f References the change rate. z.B. 0.1, 1.4, 4.3...

^g References the date format. z.B. DD:MM:YYYY

^h References the datetime format. z.B. DD:MM:YYYY HH:MM:SS

Symbole	Regel
apply_pattern_output_stmt	identifier "=" output_name new_line
assignment_stmt	(identifier list_index) codeblock_var_init
identifier	codeblock_var referential_var ⁱ
list_index	identifier "[" number_term "]"
list_append	identifier "." append "("term")"
list_remove	identifier "." remove "("number_term")"
query_selected_table	(metamodel_name.class_name input input_name input list input_name) as alias_name
query_join_stmt	join query_selected_table on (reference alias_name.reference_name attribute alias_name.attribute_name) "=" (reference alias_name.reference_name attribute alias_name.attribute_name)
query_select_command	select [distinct] from query_selected_table {query_join_stmt} ^{0...*} [where bool_term]
extra_stmt	extra extra_name new_line type data_type new_line description text_term new_line [defaultvalue term new_line] endextra new_line
expected_stmt	expected input_name.attribute_name [new_line] [defaultvalue term] [new_line] endexpected new_line
referential_var	local_var global_var attribute status input_name output_name

ⁱ Referential variables are references to variables in the surrounding, graphical code of the module. Name changes in the module are applied in the code block. The names of the referential variables correspond to the logical names (not the Id) of the referenced variables.

Symbole	Regel
codeblock_var local_var global_var dataset query_table query_attribute table status sub metamodel_name enum_name literal_name class_name operation_name attribute_name reference_name datatype_name pattern_name input_name output_name precondition_name extra_name alias_name	(letter "_") {letter digit "_"}
if_else_stmt	if bool_term then new_line {stmt} ⁺ [else new_line {stmt} ⁺] endif
loop_stmt	loop codeblock_var "=" (number_term) to (number_term) new_line {stmt} ⁺ [breakif identifier ^j] endloop
foreach_stmt	foreach table in dataset new_line {stmt} ⁺ [breakif identifier ^k] endforeach

^j typ boolean

^k type boolean

Symbole	Regel
case_stmt	<code>case case_term new_line {when term new_line {stmt}+} [default new_line {stmt}] endcase</code>
try_catch_stmt	<code>try new_line {stmt}+ catch ["(" err_number¹ ["," err_text] ")"] new_line {stmt} endtry</code>
go_subroutine	<code>gosub sub</code>
subroutine ^m	<code>sub sub new_line {stmt}+ endsub</code>
err_text err_number	codeblock_var
term	money_term datetime_term number_term text_term bool_term null_term metamodel_term identifier list_term linst_index
bool_term	identifier bool "(" bool_term ")" condition (bool_term {bool_operator bool_term}+) (bool_not bool_term)
number_term	identifier number "(" number_term ")" (number_term {number_operator number_term}+)
money_term	identifier money "(" money_term ")" (money_term {plusminus_operator money_term}+) (money_term {multdiv_operator number_term}+)
datetime_term	identifier datetime "(" datetime_term ")" (datetime_term {plusminus_operator datetime_term}+)
text_term	identifier text "(" text_term ")" (text_term {plus_operator text_term }+)
case_term	number_term text_term

¹ Parameters of the catch block must be declared outside the try_catch_stmt.

^m Subroutines are not reentrant (recursion is not possible).

Symbole	Regel
bool_not	not
comp_operator	">=" ">" "==" "<=" "<" "<>" like ^P
multdiv_operator	"*" "/"
plus_operator	"+"
minus_operator	"-"

^P Only for data types text and date

7. Sample program

Below is a short example program to illustrate and verify the rules described above.

posity-metamodel.lemon file

```
metamodel PosityMetamodel
class Table
  attribute Name
    type text
    default ""
  endattribute
  reference AttributeOfTable
    type TableAttribute
    ordered false
    unique false
    keys TableAttribute.Name
    lowerbound 0
    upperbound *
  endreference
  /*TODO Complete Table*/
endclass
class TableAttribute
  attribute Name
    type text
    default ""
  endattribute
  reference TableOfAttribute
    type Table
    ordered false
    unique true
    keys Table.Name
    lowerbound 0
    upperbound 1
  endreference
  /*TODO Complete TableAttribute*/
endclass
class ModuleEvent
  /*TODO Complete ModuleEvent*/
endclass
class ProcessEvent
  /*TODO Complete ProcessEvent*/
endclass
class Process
  /*TODO Complete Process*/
endclass
class OrganizationRole
  /*TODO Complete OrganizationRole*/
endclass
endmetamodel
```

save_event.lemon file

```
import PosityMetamodel from ../posity-metamodel.lemon
import CreateEventPattern from ./event.lemon

pattern CreateSaveEventPattern
  metadata
    name "Create Save Event"
    description "This pattern creates a Posity Save Event"
    keywords "General use", "Posity", "Save Data"
  endmetadata

  //We define the inputs of the pattern
  input isModifiedRecordsSaved
    type bool
    description "" /*TODO add description*/
    defaultvalue true
```

```

endinput

input isNewRecordsSaved
  type bool
  description "" /*TODO add description*/
  defaultvalue true
endinput

input isDeletedRecordsSaved
  type bool
  description "" /*TODO add description*/
  defaultvalue true
endinput

//We define the preconditions of the pattern (if needed)

//We define the outputs of the pattern
output saveEvent
  type PosityMetamodel.ModuleEvent
  description "Contains a Save Event."
endoutput

apply
  //Apply an existing pattern
  applypattern CreateEventPattern
    having as input
      isButtonGenerated = ask
      eventName = "Save"
      isAccessible = ask
      isClosingUseCase = false
      eventDescription = "Saves all data"
      tables = ask
      minimumRole = ask
    having as output
      saveEvent = event
    endapplypattern
  saveEvent.Section = "all sections"
  saveEvent.ID = "Save"
  saveEvent.Type = "Save"
  saveEvent.saveModifiedRecords = isModifiedRecordsSaved
  saveEvent.saveNewRecords = isNewRecordsSaved
  saveEvent.saveDeletedRecords = isDeletedRecordsSaved
endapply
endpattern

```

event.lemon file

```

import PosityMetamodel from ../posity-metamodel.lemon

pattern CreateEventPattern
  metadata
    name "Create Event"
    description "This pattern creates a Posity Event"
    keywords "General use", "Posity", "Event"
  endmetadata

  //We define the inputs of the pattern
  input isButtonGenerated
    type bool
    description "" /*TODO Add description*/
    defaultvalue false
  endinput

  input eventName
    type text
    description "" /*TODO add description*/
  endinput

  input isAccessible
    type bool
    description "" /*TODO add description*/

```

```

        defaultvalue false
    endinput

    input isClosingUseCase
        type bool
        description "" /*TODO add description*/
        defaultvalue false
    endinput

    input eventDescription
        type text
        description "" /*TODO add description*/
    endinput

    inputlist tables
        type PosityMetamodel.Table
        description "" /*TODO add description*/
        defaultvalue []
    endinputlist

    input baseEvent
        type PosityMetamodel.ProcessEvent
        description "" /*TODO add description*/
        defaultvalue null
    endinput

    input callProcess
        type PosityMetamodel.Process
        description "" /*TODO add description*/
        defaultvalue null
    endinput

    input minimumRole
        type PosityMetamodel.OrganizationRole
        description "" /*TODO add description*/
        defaultvalue null
    endinput

    //We define the preconditions of the pattern (if needed)

    //We define the outputs of the pattern
    output event
        type PosityMetamodel.ModuleEvent
        description "Contains a Event."
    endoutput

    apply
        event.generateButton = isButtonGenerated
        event.Name = eventName
        event.accessible = isAccessible
        event.closeUseCase = isClosingUseCase
        event.Description = eventDescription
        foreach table in tables
            add table to event.tableAndProcessRelationship
        endforeach
        if baseEvent <> null
            event.inheritEvent = baseEvent
        endif
        if callProcess <> null
            event.callingProcess = callProcess
        endif
        if minimumRole <> null
            event.minimumRole = minimumRole
        endif
    endapply
endpattern

```